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Severe hyperphosphatemia and hypocalcemia in an elderly woman due to very high dose of enema fleet

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Abstract

The use of sodium phosphate fleet enemas is often accompanied by toxicity, especially when there are predisposing factors in the patient or in cases of overdose. An 80-year-old woman is presented, who, after emergency surgery for a ventral hernia, was taken enemas fleet (1x2/24h for 5 days), to avoid postoperative constipation (surgeon's instructions). After the use of the enemas, she was diagnosed with severe hyperphosphatemia (serum phosphorus 21.4 mg/dl), heavy hypocalcemia (total serum calcium 4.4 mg/dl), severe left heart failure and exacerbation of the chronic renal failure that she had and knew. She was treated with high doses of calcium and hemodialysis, but despite surviving, her renal function did not improve, and she remained on a chronic conventional dialysis program. It occurred because both the treating surgeon was unaware of the contraindications to the use of the drug (patient had most of them) and its dosage, and because the instructions for use of the drug do not include, even minimally, the contraindications and side effects, especially in certain groups of patients.

It is concluded that toxicity from sodium phosphate fleet enemas exists and is associated with severe clinical and laboratory manifestations (severe hyperphosphatemia, hypocalcemia, renal and heart failure) and can be treated with both calcium administration and hemodialysis.

Keywords

Sodium phosphate enema, hyperphosphatemia, hypocalcemia, end stage renal disease, haemodialysis, QT interval

Introduction

The ability of normal kidneys to remove phosphate is huge, since even the intake of 4,000 mg/24 hours, they can eliminate. Laxatives of phosphate solutions are particularly popular for the treatment of constipation. They achieve defecation through dilation of the rectum (due to the osmotic movement of water into the intestinal lumen), which is why they are called "osmotic laxatives" and because the increasing intestinal motility, through direct stimulation of its smooth muscle fibers [1].

In 2006, the FDA, following published cases of side effects from the use of sodium phosphate enemas (acute kidney injury), recommended caution and the

inclusion of a consent document when preparing for endoscopy, following the advice of medical societies. In December 2008, the FDA again required the labeling of the risks of taking the drug in a special context in its instructions for use and at the same time its voluntary withdrawal from the market, where although the prototype was eventually withdrawn, the generic continued to be in circulation [2]. Finally, in 2014, the FDA introduced another label in the instructions, which stated that no more than one dose of the drug should be administered within 24 hours, for the treatment of constipation, because it can cause rare, but serious complications from the kidneys, heart, and even death [3,4], as well as warnings about the co-administration with diuretics, angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors, angiotensin receptor blockers, and nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) [5]. However, in the medicine used in our patient (Cooper enema 125 ml/phial, which contained 6 grams of $\text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 16 grams of $\text{NaH}_2\text{PO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, i.e. approximately 6,600 mg of inorganic phosphate), the instructions for use do not they reported any restrictions, such as in the elderly, patients with heart or renal failure, with constipation, hypertension, in use of certain medications that lead to hypovolemia (e.g. diuretics), in patients with a recent heart attack, with electrolyte disorders, nor of course clear dosage instructions "it suggests for the accuracy a dose of 60-120 ml once as directed by the doctor".

Case presentation

An 80-year-old woman was brought to the emergency department (ED) by her family with severe abdominal pain due to a strangulated abdominal hernia, which was treated invasively (using local anesthesia). As part of the surgical clinic's protocol for bowel cleansing (to avoid postoperative constipation), two daily enemas of Cooper's fleet enemas of 125 ml (contains approximately 6,600 mg of phosphate/phial) were then performed for 5 days. From her previous history, the patient was diabetic, had hyperthyroidism, heart failure, coronary artery disease, chronic renal failure, severe mitral regurgitation and arterial hypertension for whose she was receiving carbimazole tabl 5 mg/24h, glimepiride tabl 1 mg/24h, irbesartan (tabl 300 mg/24h), nifedipine CR tabl 30 mg x 2/24h and carvedilol tabl 25 mg in the morning and 12.5 mg in the evening. Upon admission, irbesartan was discontinued and cardiologists included in the treatment furosemide tabl 20 mgx2/24h and omeprazole tabl 20 mg/24h.

On the 5th postoperative day, the surgeons noted a decrease in diuresis and deterioration of renal function, and for this reason, a nephrological assessment was requested. During the examination, it was found that the patient was anuric,

dehydrated with dyspnea (orthopnea), tachypnea (pulmonary edema), hypotension (blood pressure 88/47 mmHg), 74 beats/min and a weak pulse. On auscultation, she had crackles (rales) in both lungs (a sign of pulmonary edema). Laboratory tests revealed severe hyperphosphatemia (serum phosphate 21.4 mg/dl) with severe hypocalcemia (total serum calcium 4.4 mg/dl), hypoproteinemia (serum proteins 5.5 g/dl, albumin 3.1 g/dl), C-reactive protein (CRP) 40 mg/L (normally <5 mg/L), hematocrit (Hct) 27.5%, hemoglobin (Hb) 8.8 g/dl, white blood cells (WBC) 13,200/mm³ and parathyroid hormone 430.4 pg/ml (normal <65 pg/ml), while arterial blood gases revealed pH 7.19, PaO₂ 60 mmHg, PaCO₂ 32 mmHg, HCO₃⁻ 11.9 mEq/L and lactate 0.9 mmol/L (high anion gap metabolic acidosis, with partial respiratory compensation) (Table 1).

					Beginning of dialysis				
Date	1/6/14	2/6/14	3/6/14	4/6/14	5/6/14	6/6/14	7/6/14	9/6/14	10/6/14
Ht (%)	27.1	28.2	-	27.5	26.7	28.4	25.7	25.7	29.7
Hb (g/dl)	8.9	9.2	-	8.8	8.9	9.6	8.6	9.9	10.2
WBC (mm ³)	10,400	18,100	-	14,400	13,200	14,000	13,300	8,890	9,700
Glucose (mg/dl)	105	120	168	120	-	157	245	142	161
Urea (mg/dl)	129	195	152	195	184	92	91	102	98
Creatinine (mg/dl)	2,5	4.1	4.7	4.1	5.3	2.3	3.2	3.9	4.0
Potassium (mEq/L)	4,6	4.6	4.2	4.6	3.8	3.4	3.7	4	3.9
Sodium (mEq/L)	142	145	147	146	150	145	146	148	146
Calcium (mg/dl)	-	4.4	4.6	4.4	4.3	6.7	6.9	7.1	7.1
Phosphate (mg/dl)	-	-	18.5	21.4	19.2	6.6	4.4	4.0	3.0

Table 1: Hematological and biochemical parameters before and after the start of hemodialysis (all values are before the hemodialysis sessions)

Due to the very low blood pressure and because it was considered that any increase in blood bicarbonates (which would aim to improve acidosis and therefore cardiac output) would aggravate hypocalcemia and that the attempt to increase serum calcium would improve cardiac function and blood pressure, it was decided to initially treat conservatively. Therapeutically, therefore, antihypertensive treatment (nifedipine and furosemide) was discontinued, antibiotics were changed due to leukocytosis and increased CRP (from cefuroxime to piperacillin-tazobactam + teicoplanin), 5%

dextrose serum 100 ml with 6 ampules of calcium gluconate 10% twice/24h was administered and a second solution distill water (100 ml) with 100 mEq HCO_3^- , which began to be administered after 50% of the solution with calcium was given and 4 amps of furosemide of 20 mg were administered at once (without improvement in diuresis).

On the 6th postoperative day, a double-lumen dialysis catheter was placed in the right femoral vein, and a 2-hour dialysis session was performed, while the administration of 5% D/W solution with 6 amps of calcium gluconate/24h was continued. Conventional hemodialysis was performed with a polysulfone filter (PS130), surface area 1.3 m², dialysate with 33 mEq/L bicarbonates and 6 mEq/L calcium (with administration of 10 amps of calcium gluconate during the session), without heparin and with a blood flow of 200 ml/min and dialysate flow of 500 ml/min. Two hours after the end of the session, hemodialysis was repeated for another two hours (the goal was to remove fluid (ultrafiltrate), improve the pH of hyperphosphatemia and hypocalcemia).

Figure 1: Changes in serum calcium and phosphate during the first 48 hours on dialysis

On the 7th postoperative day, hemodialysis was repeated (again with administration of calcium solution during the session), as well as on the 8th day and then continued with a program 3 dialysis sessions per week (Fig. 1 shows the changes in serum phosphate and calcium during the first 48h). Table 2 shows the changes in blood gases before the start of dialysis and for the following 4 days.

Date	4/6/14 (+4 L O ₂)	5/6/14	5/6/14	5/6/14	5/6/14 (+2 L O ₂)	6/6/14	7/6/14	9/6/14
Time	21:35	07:30 (beginning of dialysis 11:55)	14:19	16:28	18:42	18:10	09:02	12:36
pH	7.19	7.29	7.42	7.43	7.47	7.45	7.43	7.45
PaCO ₂ (mmHg)	32	28	33	28	32	32	36	36
PaO ₂ (mmHg)	60	100	82	81	72	69	69	76
HCO ₃ ⁻ (mEq/L)	11.9	13.5	21.4	18.6	23.3	22.2	23.9	24.8
Lactate (mmol/L)	0.9	0.9	0.8	1.2	0.9	1.2	1.1	-
SaO ₂ (%)	83	97	96	96	95	94	94	95.9

Table 2: Changes in blood gases before the start of dialysis and up to the 4th day thereafter

During her hospitalization, the patient had alternating episodes of dyspnea (orthopnea), she almost constantly had icon of pulmonary edema in the middle and lower lung fields. 24h after the first dialysis session, when she was able to talk, after our questioning, she reported numbness around the mouth and mainly in the upper and less in the lower extremities. Her condition gradually improved, however, her renal function did not improve, and she ultimately remained in the end stage of renal failure, for which she continued conventional hemodialysis. Ten days after the diagnosis of sodium phosphate toxicity, the patient suffered an acute myocardial infarction, for which she was hospitalized in the cardiology clinic, from where she was discharged in an improved condition.

The simple kidney-ureter-bladder (KUB) X-ray performed one month after the episode of sodium phosphate toxicity diagnosis was normal (no calcifications in the kidney area).

Discussion

After the use of phosphate fleet enemas, significant amounts of hypotonic solutions are lost so dehydration, hypovolemia, and hypernatremia are not uncommon side effects of their use.

Hyperphosphatemia following phosphate fleet enemas had been described in approximately 12 cases up to 2007 [5], while in a one-year retrospective study of 269 constipated patients who underwent therapeutic enemas in the ED, one case of hyperphosphatemia was found, which was fatal [6]. Increased serum phosphate levels have been found after the use of sodium phosphate enemas, even in individuals with

normal renal function [7]. Thus, asymptomatic hyperphosphatemia (an increase in phosphorus 2-3 times above normal levels) has been found in 25% of cases of patients with normal renal function who received phosphate preparations as laxatives [8]. Ori et al. retrospectively found severe hyperphosphatemia in 11 patients with fleet enemas toxicity (serum phosphate up to 45 mg/dl) and severe hypocalcemia (total serum calcium up to 2.0 mg/dl) [1].

This hyperphosphatemia is not due to renal retention, but to increased acute absorption of phosphate from the intestine. It is important to note that the phosphate is generally absorbed in duodenum and jejunum, but colonic absorption is possible secondary due to high concentrations in the rectum [9]. Of course, acidosis also increases serum phosphorus levels, through a decrease in oxidative phosphorylation and the release of phosphate from the intracellular compartment. In a study with 45 subjects, it was found that an increase in the length of stay of the enemas in the intestine was associated with transient hyperphosphatemia, regardless of the volume of the solution administered [10]. This was also the case in our patient, who, after the administration of 10 fleet enemas, reached to have a serum phosphorus of 21.4 mg/dl at the time of the nephrological assessment.

Hyperphosphatemia causes hypocalcemia through: a) decreased production of $1,25(\text{OH})_2\text{D}_3$, b) precipitation of the calcium-phosphate complex, out of bones, in both the intercellular and extracellular space [11], in the distal tubules [12], as well as in the joints, subcutaneous soft tissue and other tissues and c) decreased absorption of calcium from the intestine, possibly due to a direct effect of phosphate. Our patient had severe hypocalcemia which causes hypotension (which is generally very rarely observed in these cases) [5] and reduced myocardial contractility (of course, acidosis was also responsible).

In the electrocardiogram (ECG) in case of hypocalcemia, a prolongation of the QT interval (normal range <0.40 msec) is rarely observed. This was found in a study in 7/11 patients [1] with hypocalcemia from sodium phosphate solution, which was also noted by others [13], as well as by us (QT 0.572 on the day of the first nephrological assessment) (Fig. 2). There is evidence that elevated serum phosphate levels are directly toxic, although cardiac arrest has been described with serum phosphorus levels of 8.4 mg/dl [14]. Hypocalcemia can lead to tetany and cardiac arrest and sometimes death.

Figure 2: Our patient's ECG, showing the prolonged QT interval

Markowitz et al. reported 21 cases of acute kidney injury from sodium phosphate enema [15]. Acute kidney injury from sodium phosphate is rare, although most published cases were due to high doses of the drug [16,17]. One study found that it occurred after usual doses, but also after increased doses in elderly patients, with or without renal impairment [1].

There is also acute reversible phosphate nephropathy. This is less insidious with reversible renal injury. It is characterized by hyperphosphatemia and hypocalcemia with clinical symptoms of cardiovascular collapse, tetany and changes in mental functions, usually hours after oral intake of the laxative solution [7]. It seems to be due to prerenal causes or acute tubular necrosis and not to the toxic effect of phosphate. In this case, the use of ACE inhibitors additionally worsens glomerular autoregulation, in patients with hypovolemic states (such as the elderly). In hypovolemic patients, the proximal intense reabsorption of water and sodium causes greater intratubular precipitation of calcium-phosphate complexes in the distal tubules [18], where large amounts of phosphate reach. The precipitation of this complex is due to the phosphate load leading to nephrocalcinosis [2].

Although computer tomography (CT) is the most sensitive imaging technique for investigating renal calcification, in KUB severe cortical calcification seen weeks or months after ischemic renal injury suggests renal cortical necrosis and is associated with non-recovery of renal function, which we have seen in our patient.

There has been published case of toxicity from phosphate enemas in an elderly patient with normal renal function who died [19] or survived [20], and in a patient with chronic kidney failure in whom serum phosphate levels reached at 18 mg/dl and he survive [21]. Several cases of toxicity from overdose phosphate enemas have also been published. Others developed toxicity after receiving one fleet enema every hour for 6 hours [22], others after 6 doses of sodium phosphate in 12 hours [17] and others with 2 fleet with double dosage dose [23], from that used by our patient.

Our patient had very severe hyperphosphatemia (21.4 mg/dl) and severe hypocalcemia (total calcium 4.4 mg/dl) at the time of diagnosis of phosphate toxicity, with concomitant cardiological disorders (pulmonary edema and hypotension) and severe high anion gap metabolic acidosis (the anion gap in phosphate toxicity increases due to hyperphosphatemia and hypocalcemia) [1], conditions that make therapeutic management extremely difficult. Because it is difficult to administer calcium to improve hypotension and reduce myocardial contractility due to hypocalcemia, just as it is difficult to initiate hemodialysis due to hypotension, but also because the improvement of acidosis from the bicarbonates of the dialysate will further reduce ionized calcium [14]. Of course, in the state of pulmonary edema that the patient was in, it was also difficult to administer any solution in the form of an intravenous infusion (risk of exacerbation of pulmonary edema). This is why the treatment of hypocalcemia was chosen initially (despite the risk of out of bones deposits of calcium-phosphate complexes), because it was considered that this could be tolerated by our patient and will be improved, and then with the application of hemodialysis, partial improvement of the acidosis could be achieved, so that with these manipulations cardiac output could be improved, as was done.

Predisposing factors for the occurrence of toxicity from phosphate fleet enemas include decreased intestinal motility (accompanied by increased phosphate absorption), constipation, congestive heart failure, recent ischemic heart disease (last 6 months) [24,25], pre-existing chronic renal failure (stages 3-5), old age (>65 years) [24,26] (elderly people have constipation 5 times more often compared to younger people, due to the effect of medications, immobility and the attenuation of the urge to defecate) [27], taking certain medications that reduce renal perfusion, such as diuretics, ACE inhibitors, angiotensin AT-1 receptor blockers, calcium channel

blockers and NSAIDs [28], women, perhaps because they have a smaller physique and lower glomerular filtration rate (GFR) than men and other comorbid conditions, such as hypertension, diabetes, liver failure, hypovolemia, etc. [8,29,30], most of which our patient had.

Absolute contraindications for the use of phosphate fleet enemas include pregnancy, age <18 years, stage 3 - 5 chronic kidney disease, inability to adequately ingest fluids, pre-existing electrolyte disorder, ascites, symptomatic congestive heart failure, recent ischemic heart disease, and unstable angina, many of which our patient also had [31-33].

Overdose with fleet enemas had been reported in 8 cases up to 2007 and in this review, of the deaths identified, (4 were in individuals under 18 years of age and most occurred in those who had received more than 2 fleet enemas) [24]. The maximum number of phosphate enemas given in the literature was 8 in an 86-year-old patient [34], however our patient received totally ten of them.

Toxicity from fleet enemas is generally severe. Life-threatening or fatal hypocalcemia and hyperphosphatemia have been reported sporadically [35]. Several deaths have been reported from the use of phosphate solutions as laxatives [36,37]. Thus, the mortality of phosphate toxicity varies (5/11 included in one study) [1], while other isolated cases have survived [7,13,38]. In general, the reported mortality of severe hyperphosphatemia due to solutions with phosphate salts in enemas is approximately 33% [39] and was reported at serum phosphate from 16-30 mg/dl [5].

In terms of treatment, when there are severe manifestations of hypocalcemia, the administration of calcium is a priority. It is believed that under such conditions (life-threatening), the administration of calcium with caution is indicated (in parallel with phosphate reduction procedures), since it was found that the risk of deposition of these salts in soft tissues is much smaller, in comparison to the risk of cardiovascular consequences of hypocalcemia [14]. The administration of calcium as mentioned in hyperphosphatemia with hypocalcemia is a dilemma [7]. Thus, calcium was used to treat hypocalcemia whenever there was a risk to the patient's life [13,17,21,40]. Finally, although metastatic deposits of the calcium-phosphate complex have been described in patients, no case has been published of a patient with hyperphosphatemia treated with calcium who exhibited such a deposit, a fact that we also agree with, as we administered a large amount of calcium.

In cases of severe toxicity from phosphate solutions, the application of hemodialysis is indicated, mainly in patients with hyperphosphatemia and renal failure,

where together with calcium administration, these two actions appear to be lifesaving [1,7,22,41], as was our case.

Our case differs from the published ones in that: a) the patient, while having many contraindications to receiving the phosphate fleet enema, nevertheless received twice the daily dose for 5 days, which is the largest reported in the literature, b) her manifestations and laboratory findings were very severe (pulmonary edema, hypotension, severe hypocalcemia), which prevented the application of the hemodialysis, while calcium administration was also dangerous (due to severe hyperphosphatemia), c) despite the severe hypocalcemia, her manifestations, apart from hypotension, were perioral and extremity numbness, and d) despite her serious general condition, she survived.

It is concluded that toxicity from sodium phosphate fleet enema exists and that both doctors who are not fully informed and the companies that produce and supply them are responsible for it. It is associated with severe hyperphosphatemia, hypocalcemia, renal and heart failure and can be treated with both calcium administration and hemodialysis.

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